

When to use *Italics* or Underline VS “Double Quote”?

Being a student of literature, apart from grasping the literature from an advanced perspective, students find their hard times in confusion about the usage of Underline and “Double Quote” while writing any name of work (artistic or literary or scientific) in the answer script. In this blog, I am going to create a short tutorial concerning the practice of utilising proper methods with examples.

1. When to use underline or *Italics*?

- Any stand-out name of the work should be used with underlining or italics. According to MLA*, “When a work that is normally italicized (such as a novel, play, or serialized graphic narrative) appears in a larger work [] both titles appear in italics” (2021 2.108).
- **Example** (extracted from MLA):

Euripides’s play *The Trojan Women* appears in the collection *Ten Plays*, translated by Paul Roche.

Did you use the edition of Shakespeare’s *Hamlet* found on the *Internet Shakespeare Editions* website?

The graphic narrative *David Boring* was serialized in three issues of Daniel Clowes’s comic book *Eightball*.

Note: Usually, works that are collections or bigger stand-out works such as epic, novels etc will be written either using Italics or Underline.

Since Italics can not properly be used with handwritten notes, it is preferable to use Underline while writing using a pen or pencil.

• When to use “Double Quote”?

The quotation is used for the works which are shorter and contained in a larger collection, or a part of a bigger work. Usually, works like essays, short stories, and articles.

Example (source: MLA):

Journal article

“Why Milton Is Not an Iconoclast”

Magazine article

“When Michelangelo Went to Constantinople”

Encyclopedia article

“Etruscan”

Essay in a collection

“The Fiction of Langston Hughes”

Short story

“The Lottery”

Poem

“Afterimages”

Chapter in a book

“The American Economy before the Civil War”

Page on a website

“The Princess Bride You Don’t Know”

Episode of a television or streaming series

“Women’s Work”

Song

“Somewhere over the Rainbow”

Video of a song

“Hold Up”

Lecture

“The Future of the Public Mission of Universities”

3. Even there are some types of works which do not need any specific formatting according to MLA:

a. Scripture

- **Example** (extracted from MLA):
- Bible
 - Genesis
 - Gospels
 - Koran or Quran or Qur’an
 - Old Testament
 - Talmud
 - Upanishads

b. Laws, acts, and other political documents

- **Example** (extracted from MLA):
- Bill of Rights
- Declaration of Independence
- Improving Broadband Access for Veterans Act of 2016
- Magna Carta
- Treaty of Trianon

c. Musical compositions identified by form, number, and key

- **Example** (extracted from MLA):
- Beethoven's Symphony No. 7 in A, Opus 92
Vivaldi's Concerto for Two Trumpets and Strings in C, RV539

d. Columns and titled categories in periodicals and on websites

- **Example** (extracted from MLA):
- Ask the MLA (titled category of posts on a website or blog)
The Ethicist (newspaper column)

d. Titled print publication series

- **Example** (extracted from MLA):
- Approaches to Teaching World Literature
A Song of Ice and Fire

e. Informally titled series

["Informally titled series of all kinds are usually referred to by the title of the foundational work or the main character featured in the series. When the title of the series includes the main character's name, italics or roman typeface is acceptable as long as styling is applied consistently" (MLA)]

- **Example** (extracted from MLA)
Star Wars movies
Harry Potter novels
Harry Potter novels

But titles of shows that air on television and stream online (often called

series) are italicized.

- **Example** (extracted from MLA):
- The Umbrella Academy

f. Conferences, courses, workshops, and events

International Symposium on Cultural Diplomacy 2015
MLA Annual Convention
Introduction to Anthropology
Geographic Information Analysis Workshop
Edinburgh International Festival

g. Terms designating divisions of a work

Note: According to MLA, "Terms designating the divisions of a work are not capitalized, italicized, or put in quotation marks when used in your prose (The author says in her preface . . . ; In canto 32 Ariosto writes . . .)".

- **Example** (extracted from MLA):
- act 4
appendix
bibliography

canto 32
chapter 2
index
introduction
list of works cited
preface
scene 7
stanza 20

h. Earthworks, ancient artworks, and buildings

- **Example** (extracted from MLA):
 - Arch of Titus
 - Empire State Building
 - Fallingwater
 - Great Serpent Mound
 - Great Wall of China
 - Stonehenge
 - Taj Mahal
 - Venus de Milo

Note:

* I have used MLA to mean MLA Handbook 9th Edition

For further study, check:

MLA Handbook, 9th Edition. Modern Language Association of America, 2021.